

Original Research Report

Awareness of DASH Diet among Hypertensive Patients in Ido-Osi Local Government Hospitals, Ekiti State Nigeria

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Abstract: The study investigated the level of awareness of the DASH diet among hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi local government hospitals, Ekiti State Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with three specific purposes, three research questions, and one null hypothesis to guide the study. The population of the study is 282 hypertensive patients, which include both in and outpatients from the seven local government hospitals who were present at the moment of data collection. No sampling technique was used as the whole of the population was used. A 27- item structured and validated questionnaire was used in the data collection and the data analysis was done using Mean and Standard deviation by SPSS version 20.0 and ANOVA for the analysis of the one null hypothesis. Cronbach Alpha Reliability Method was used to determine the internal consistency and 0.81 was obtained. The major findings of the study are the poor level of awareness of the DASH diet as revealed in their poor consumption of fruits and vegetables, consumption of red meat, sugars, sweets, saturated fats, and cholesterols among others. It also reveals that factors like illiteracy and economic factor among others challenge their awareness about the DASH diet. Strategies developed to increase awareness of the DASH diet among others include nutrition education and the installation of registered dietitians in government hospitals.

Keywords: Awareness, Diet, Dietary Approach to Stop Hypertension (DASH), Hospital, Hypertension

1. Introduction

WHO (2021) defined hypertension as diseases condition in which the increase force of blood flow against the arterial walls of the circulatory system constantly raises its pressure. It is a ‘silent killer’ disease with many risk factors and complications (Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research). Epidemiological study by WHO (2021) reported that an estimated 1.28 billion adults aged 30-79 years worldwide have hypertension. Hence, the major cause of premature death worldwide. One of the global targets for non-communicable diseases is to reduce the prevalence of hypertension by 33% between 2010 and 2030 (WHO, 2021). Study by Ogbera and Ekpebegh (2014) has revealed that an attempt to manage and treat hypertension by its patients often imposes a serious financial burden on them and places them on the high risk of death at any time if not properly controlled.

Owing to the above fact, Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) diet by clinical nutrition advancement was discovered to control and manage the disease condition without changes in body weight (Pescatello et al., 2004). DASH diet has been proven to be the best diet in effectiveness in preventing and managing diet-related diseases including hypertension (Kerley, 2018). It is a healthy eating plan with emphasis on high potassium, calcium, magnesium, fiber and protein, no saturated fats and low sodium (Juraschek et al., 2016). It encourages high intake of fruits and vegetable; whole grains; fat-free dairy products, lean meat, poultry and fishes; nuts, seeds and legumes, low fats and oil; and little or no sweets and added sugars while excluding processed and canned meats as they are high in carcinogenic compounds (Urrico, 2018). Apart from its ability to manage hypertension, researchers showed that it reduces the risk of chronic kidney diseases, diabetes type 2 and cancer (Chiavaroli, et al., 2019); increases mental health (Van den Brink, Brouwer-Brolsma, Berenden, & Van de Re, 2019) and decreases overall death rate (Soltani, Arablou, Jayedi, & Salehi-Abargouei, 2020).

Despite the above listed nutritional and health benefits, certain factors affect the level of its awareness among hypertensive patients and these include poor spreading and poor translation of nutritional information regarding DASH diets (Steinberg, Bennett & Svetkey, 2017); socioeconomic factors such as financial and educational level (Bloch, 2017) and poor nutrition education and lack of awareness of the role of registered dieticians in diet related disease management (Steinberg, et al., 2017). Owing to these perceived challenges, strategies should be adopted to promote strong awareness of the DASH diet to the hypertensive patients.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Hypertension is now a prevalent medical condition in almost all parts of Nigeria especially in Ido-Osi local government over the last decade. Not only that, the danger associated with this medical condition is that it usually comes with array of other clinical illnesses which usually places the patients on regular hospital visit, financial burden and death in most cases. As a result, clinical nutritionists have succeeded globally in developing relevant measures towards controlling its effects on patients by devising DASH diet plan, which is underutilized by most patients in developing countries like Nigeria despite its effectiveness in managing hypertension. Most patients in Ido-Osi local government areas in Ondo state are not even aware of it. They solely use drugs in managing their condition, which not all of them can afford. Because of the poor utilization due to poor level of awareness, they incur upon themselves financial burden and have their condition degenerated to strokes and loss of their lives in the process.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study is to determine the level of awareness of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study include to:

- (a) Determine the extent of awareness of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State.
- (b) Examine the benefits of challenges of utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State.
- (c) Determine strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What is the extent of awareness of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State?
- (b) What are the challenges of utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State?
- (c) What are the strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State?

1.4. Research Hypothesis

One null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean rating of hypertensive patients attending government hospitals Ido-Osi LGA on the extent of awareness of DASH diet based on their level of education.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

A descriptive survey design was used in the study. This was chosen because the study sought to collect data on the perception of a given population in a systematic way such that the findings are expected to be generalized to the entire population (Nworgu, 2006).

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The ethics approval of the study was done by the Department of Clinical Research of Federal medical center Ido-Osi LGA, Ekiti State, Nigeria as ethic of privacy and confidentiality of patients was ensured in accordance with the world medical association declaration of Helsinki. The participants gave their informed consent orally before completing the survey.

2.2. Area of the Study

The area of the study was Ido-Osi L.G.A Hospitals, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The Hospitals were selected for the study, as they are mostly affordable, recognized and mostly accessible hospitals by the authors compared to other government hospitals in Ekiti State Nigeria.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for the study consisted of 282 (142 males, 140 females) both in and out-hypertensive patients present at the time of visitation in the respective government hospitals available

Ido-Ekiti LGA Ekiti State Nigeria. The total number of the hypertensive patients was 282 and all were used in the study. Table 1. Shows the detail of the population of the study.

Table 1. Population of the study

S/N	Names of hospitals and Health centers	Number of Males	Number of females	Total
1	General Hospital, Ifaki Ekiti.	31	26	57
2	General Hospital Otun Ekiti.	36	24	60
3	Federal medical center Ido Ekiti.	25	40	65
4	Ido-Ekiti health center.	15	18	33
5	Ifaki-Ekiti health center.	12	9	21
6	Usi-Ekiti health center.	6	13	19
7	Ayetoro-Ekiti health center.	17	10	27
8	Total population	142	140	282

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A well-structured questionnaire titled Awareness of DASH Diet by Hypertensive Patients Questionnaire (ADDHPQ) with 27 items was constructed for the study by the researcher based on vast literature review using research objectives as guide. It has two sections (A and B) while B which is made up of three clusters was designed to sought out information on each of the three (3) research questions. The instrument adopted a four rating scales with response categories of; Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.49), Disagree (1.50-2.49), Agree (2.50-3.49) and Strongly Agree (3.50-4.00). Hence, any item with mean score above 2.50 will be accepted while items below 2.50 will be rejected because it is adjudged to below the criterion level of acceptance. The data collection was done by the help of three (3) research assistants who were educated on the purpose of the research and polite manner of approaching respondents to solicit honest responses from the respondents

2.4.1 Validation and Reliability of the Instrument.

The instrument was face and content validated by two experts two registered clinical dieticians in Federal Medical Centre Ido-Ekiti. Their inputs and corrections were considered and effected before the distributing to the respondents at the respective clinics to collect data. The reliability of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Method and 0.81 internal consistency was achieved which showed that the instrument is reliable.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

All the administered questionnaires were returned by the help of the researcher and three research assistants. The returned questionnaires were used for data analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The data collected were analyzed with mean and standard deviation using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) Version 20.0 while the null hypotheses were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What is the level of awareness of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of respondents on the level of awareness of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ondo state

S/NO	DASH diet statements	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	I ensure that sodium and salt are reduced highly in my meal.	3.48	0.51	Agreed
2	I take more fruits and vegetables.	2.43	0.79	Disagreed
3	I use low-fat milk.	2.48	0.94	Disagreed
4	I do not use saturated fats and cholesterol.	2.49	0.89	Disagreed
5	I do not take red meat, sweets and added sugars.	2.45	0.76	Disagreed
6	I eat food rich in high fiber, calcium and magnesium.	2.41	0.74	Disagreed
7	I use whole grains and proteins like lean meat, fish and poultry.	2.45	0.87	Disagreed
8	I do not include processed and polished foods.	3.03	0.88	Agreed
9	I include plants proteins like legumes, nuts and seeds in my diet.	2.34	0.67	Disagreed
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation.		2.62	0.48	Agreed

Note: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 2 shows that the respondents agreed to item 1 and 8, with a mean of 3.03 and 3.48 respectively. However, the respondents disagreed to items 2 – 7 and 9 with a mean range of 2.34 – 2.49. In addition, the standard deviation ranged from 0.51 – 0.94 indicating the respondents' poor degree of awareness of DASH diet.

3.2. *Research Question two:* What are the challenges of utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of respondents on the challenges of utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ondo state.

S/N	Challenges of utilization of DASH diet	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
10	Economic constraints.	3.38	0.74	Agreed
11	Difficulties in interpretation and a low understanding of nutritional facts on food labels.	3.34	0.62	Agreed
12	Poor nutrition education by nutritionists.	2.82	0.74	Agreed
13	Scarcity of Registered dietician in most of the hospitals.	2.62	0.74	Agreed
14	Inadequate supports by family members.	2.58	0.56	Agreed
15	Poor record keeping by most of the hospital workers to follow up the patients.	3.65	0.48	Agreed
16	Unprofessional counseling from most of health workers.	2.66	0.67	Agreed
17	Religious factors, which often lead to negligence to health and nutritional matters.	2.01	0.55	Disagreed
18	Age of the patients.	2.97	0.65	Agreed
19	Level of literacy.	3.15	0.67	Agreed
Cluster Mean and Standard deviation.		2.92	0.20	Agreed

Note: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 3 shows that the respondents agreed to all the suggested items on challenges except item 17 with a mean of 2.01. The agreed item statement on challenges had a mean range of 2.58 – 3.38. In addition, the standard deviation ranged from 0.48 – 0.74 indicating that there are challenges militating the use of the challenges of utilization of DASH diet by the respondents.

3.3. *Research question three:* What are the strategies to be adopted in order to promote awareness and utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of respondents on the strategies to be adopted in order to promote awareness and utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients in Ido-Osi LGA hospital in Ekiti State

S/N	Strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
20	Sensitizing the public on the role of registered dietitian in Disease management.	3.09	0.73	Agreed
21	Encouraging home gardening.	2.78	0.63	Agreed
22	Patients literacy should be considered during counseling to determine right choice of words.	3.65	0.68	Agreed
23	Video delivery during general counseling to sensitize patients on effects of failure to adhere to DASH diet.	2.89	0.64	Agreed
24	Equipping health workers with nutritional matters.	3.20	0.62	Agreed
25	Patients should be encouraged to adherently stick to DASH plan.	3.54	0.69	Agreed
26	Nutrition education on DASH diet benefits in different religious centers and community halls.	3.08	0.68	Agreed
27	Installation of the registered dietitians in government hospitals.	3.30	0.67	Agreed
	Cluster Mean and Standard deviation.	3.19	0.26	Agreed

Note: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 4 shows that the respondents agreed to all the suggested items on strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients. The agreed item statements on strategies had a mean range of 2.78 – 3.65. In addition, the standard deviation ranged from 0.62 – 0.73 indicating that the responses are all effective strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients

3.4. *Research Hypothesis*

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the mean ratings of hypertensive patients attending government hospitals Ido-Osi LGA on the level of awareness of DASH diet based on their level of education.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance of the mean responses of hypertensive patients attending government hospitals Ido-Osi LGA on the level of awareness of DASH diet based on their level of education.

S/N	Perceptions of fathers on family feeding?	Sources of Variance	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value	Rem.
1	I ensure that sodium and salt are reduced highly in my meal.	Between Groups	28.202	7	4.03	23.89	0.00	S
		Within Groups	46.210	274	0.17			
		Total	74.411	281				
2	I take more fruits and vegetables.	Between Groups	77.714	7	11.10	30.66	0.00	S
		Within Groups	99.222	274	0.36			
		Total	176.936	281				
3	I use low-fat milk.	Between Groups	115.881	7	16.55	34.77	0.00	S
		Within Groups	130.445	274	0.48			
		Total	246.326	281				
4	I do not use saturated fats and cholesterol.	Between Groups	102.465	7	14.64	32.88	0.00	S
		Within Groups	121.979	274	0.45			
		Total	224.443	281				
5	I do not take red meat, sweets and added sugars.	Between Groups	42.487	7	6.07	13.72	0.00	S
		Within Groups	121.215	274	0.44			
		Total	163.702	281				
6	I eat food rich in high fiber, calcium and magnesium.	Between Groups	34.961	7	4.99	11.68	0.00	S
		Within Groups	117.142	274	0.43			
		Total	152.103	281				
7	I use whole grains and proteins like lean meat, fish and poultry.	Between Groups	81.605	7	11.66	24.14	0.00	S
		Within Groups	132.295	274	0.48			
		Total	213.901	281				
8		Between Groups	47.553	7	6.79	11.07	0.00	S

	I do not include processed and polished foods.	Within Groups Total	168.220 215.773	274 281	0.61				
9	I include plants proteins like legumes, nuts and seeds in my diet.	Between Groups Within Groups Total	13.671 113.964 127.635	7 274 281	1.95 0.42	4.70	0.00	S	
10	Cluster Mean and Standard deviation.	Between Groups Within Groups Total	46.791 19.157 65.948	7 274 281	6.68 0.07	95.61	0.00	S	

The Table 5 shows that the items F-value ranged from 4.70 – 34.77 at (7, 274) degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.00 which is lower than 0.05 alpha value. Furthermore, the cluster F-value and p-value are 95.61 and 0.00 respectively, which is also less than 0.05 alpha value. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative upheld.

Firstly, the findings showed that the respondents agreed to the only two practices concerning DASH diet awareness level: reduction of sodium and salt in meal and inclusion of plants proteins like legumes, nuts and seeds in diet. However, they disagreed to the other seven which include among others consumption of more fruits and vegetables; use of low-fat milk; avoidance of saturated fats and cholesterol; avoidance of red meat, sweets and added sugars; calcium and magnesium and avoidance of processed and polished foods. The findings above revealed low level of awareness of DASH diet by the hypertensive patients attending Ido-Osi local government hospitals. This is in agreement with the findings by Steinberg et al. (2017) that there are observed low adherence to DASH diet despite its clinical importance in managing hypertension.

Secondly, the findings revealed that respondents agreed to all the challenges to awareness of DASH diet except religious factor. This is in agreement with the study of Bloch (2017) that factors among others such as Economic constraints; Level of literacy; Difficulties in interpretation and a low understanding of nutritional facts on food labels affects the awareness of DASH diet among the people. Therefore, it is expedients that strategies to enhance the awareness and use of DASH diet is promoted by nutritionist and home economic extension officers.

Thirdly, the findings revealed that the respondents agreed to all the strategies to be adopted in order to increase proper utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients include among others; sensitizing the public on the role of registered dietitian in Disease management; Patients literacy should be considered during counseling to determine right choice of words and equipping health workers with nutritional matters. This gives credence to the studies of Steinberg et al. (2017) on the issues of strategies that can promote the awareness and utilization of DASH diet by hypertensive patients.

Lastly, the findings showed that there is a significance difference between the mean ratings of hypertensive patients attending government hospitals Ido-Osi LGA on the level of awareness of DASH diet based on their level of education. This agrees with the study by Pescatello et al. (2004) that patients' level of literacy affects patients' awareness, and adherence to DASH diet.

The implication of the research can be clinical as it will be a veritable tool in the hands of registered dieticians in prescribing and administering diets to hypertensive patients than spending money on drugs, which is unaffordable and unhealthy. Academically, it can be useful to, Food and Nutrition teachers and Extension Officers for educating the masses on eating right. Economically, financial burdens associated in pharmacological and medical treatment of the disease condition will be eased of the patients.

Several factors limited the research process such as high cost of data analysis and publication fee, refusal of most health workers to allow the researcher to carry out the research task in their hospitals, poor compliance of the patients to the research during data collection and heavy rainfall, which barely prevented the transportation to different hospitals for data collections.

However, the researchers suggests that the study should be carried out in different location, with different design, different data collection method for further study.

4. Conclusion

One of the leading causes of death in the world today is hypertension. In a bid to curb the menace pharmacologically and medically, financial burden has been incurred upon the victims. For this cause, DASH diet was discovered, yet underutilized due to low level of awareness by the masses. The study hereby investigated the awareness level of DASH diet by hypertensive patients attending Ido-Osi local government hospitals, Ekiti State, Nigeria. According to the study, certain factors strengthens the obvious poor level of awareness of DASH diet by the hypertensive patients in above study area and these are economic constraints, scarcity of registered dietician in the hospitals, poor nutrition education among others. Strategies were adopted to increase awareness and adherence of hypertensive patients to DASH diet and this include equipping health workers with nutritional matters, Installation of the registered dietitians in government hospital, encouraging quality nutrition education among others.

However the researchers recommends among others that above strategies should be incorporated into the Nutritional policy of Ekiti State Nigeria; installation of dietitians in the hospitals by the government in the study area and encouragement of home gardening by extension officers to ensure availability of food diversity to the individuals.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors Contributions

Foluso O. Adedoyin and Nnaemeka A. Ugwuanyi designed and directed the work. Foluso O. Adedoyin conducted the research while Nnaemeka O. Ugwuanyi analyzed and interpreted the data. Both the authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript, and decided the final version of the work to be published after thorough revision.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article; further inquiries can be directed to corresponding authors.

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